

Psychiatry Diagnoses Coercion in Government

Johan Nygren, johanngrn@gmail.com

Spontaneous generation theory for bacterial infections was popular in the 1800s. It was a result of projecting causality onto a symptom. Cause onto the infection itself, because people could not see the cause, the bacteria. Eventually with the work of Louis Pasteur and John Tyndall, and the microscope, science could rise above superstition. Mental disorder, as *generatio spontanea* for “meme illness”, a false medical theory, is also projecting causality onto a symptom, because it cannot see the cause, the monopoly on violence, because the observer has **slave mentality**.

In social mammals, serotonin regulates rank in a dominance hierarchy that organizes by a pecking order. These pecking orders require certain behaviour patterns from their members, irritability towards inferiors, and anxiety towards superiors, elation on going up the hierarchy and depression on going down. In a society that organizes by a dominance hierarchy, master-slave organization, those below the ruling class are (based on behaviour patterns that have been strongly selected for) afraid of “looking the master in the eye”.

Because of instinctive anxiety towards superiors in the dominance hierarchy, those below the ruling class prefer to explain certain trends in their environment with a superstitious myth. At the same time, because of irritability towards inferiors, those higher up also prefer a similar myth. Psychiatry has evolved to fill that niche, it provides the myth that allows people to cope with coercive government, an “opium for the people”, reinforcing the dominance hierarchy by human ritual sacrifice.

The niche for Psychiatry as a mythology will exist as long as society is built on a dominance hierarchy.

References

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